

A geometric method for summing

$$S(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{-1}{(-x)^{n+1}} \quad (1)$$

for any real number $x > 1$

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Abstract

In this article I explain a geometric method that I have discovered to sum the alternating infinite series, $S(x) = \frac{1}{x} - \frac{1}{x^2} + \frac{1}{x^3} - \dots$, for any real number $x > 1$. Using this method I will show that the sum of the series must equal $\frac{1}{x+1}$. I first motivate with integer examples of 4 and 2, followed by reaching the general result for any number $x > 1$.

1 Introduction

In October 2020 I wrote a paper describing a geometric method I discovered to sum the geometric series $S(x) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{x^j}$ for all values of $x > 1$ ¹. I emailed this paper to Dr Adam Reid, my maths teacher at Tonbridge School. In return he posed me a question. The question he asked was what would be the result of $\frac{1}{x} - \frac{1}{x^2} + \frac{1}{x^3} - \dots$? I was very busy over the next few months and I never got around to thinking about it. Then on the 15th of August 2021 he wrote me again asking if I had had the chance to have a look at the alternating geometric series. On the 24th of August the solution suddenly popped into my head as I was being driven by my dad to a hearing test in Eastbourne.

¹I. Afaf, A geometric method of summing $S(x) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{x^j}$ for any real number $x > 1$, Tonbridge School Paper, (Oct 2020).

Here is how it happened. My dad asked me what it really meant to take a negative number from something. After thinking about it for a few minutes I came up with the following idea. Imagine you have a bit of something. If you take something *+ve* away then it leaves a hole in the original thing. Now if you add it back it fills that hole. But now imagine that you are taking away a *-ve* number from that thing. This is like adding a negative hole to the original thing. But a negative hole is something additional that needs to be returned back. It cannot be taken away from something that was already in that thing. As I explained this, Dr Reid's question just suddenly popped into my mind. I then immediately realised that I could also use the same geometric method I used in the October 2020 paper for this alternating series as well.

In the rest of the paper I explain how, starting with two integer examples before generalising to any $x > 1$.

2 Integer Examples

I consider here two integer examples: $x=4$, and $x=2$, respectively.

2.1 An example for $x=4$

Before we look at the alternating series, it is best to revisit the geometric series for $x = 4$, which I discussed in my previous paper. This will help us to understand the geometric method for the alternating series.

2.1.1 The geometric series for $S(4) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{4^j}$

Here we start by dividing one big square into 4 equal smaller squares. We choose 1 smaller square for the term $1/4$ in the infinite series. We leave out 2 smaller sub squares, and set aside out a 4th smaller sub square for further subdivisions for future stages. These subdivisions continue *ad infinitum*. Leaving aside the small square left for further sub divisions, we can see that we have selected $1/3$ of the overall figure at this stage. At the next stage, we now focus on the 4th small square we had set aside. We now use this for further subdivision and divide this into 4 even smaller subsquares, and set aside 1 of these for the next stage. This now gives us the next $1/16$ term of the infinite series but which is only again $1/3$ of the squares under consideration at this stage. We now continue repeating this method for ever smaller subsquares at each successive subdivision stage.

As we continue this, we keep getting successive $(1/64, 1/256, 1/1024...)$ entries of the next terms in the series by selecting $1/3$ of the squares under consideration at that stage. But if we always select only $1/3$ of the ever smaller sub squares in consideration at each stage, then the total part of the overall square chosen has to be $1/3$. This case is the easiest to see because of the symmetry of the square repeats itself in each successive subdivision.

Now just to understand my method was to choose a certain number of squares, call it C , a certain number of squares set aside for later use, call it S , a certain number of squares left out, call them L . We can see that for $x = 4$ we have $C = 1$, $S = 1$, and $L = 2$. So we can see that the answer comes from the expression $\frac{1}{3}$ is got by the expression $\frac{C}{L+C}$, when we substitute values for C and L . We can now check and see if our result is correct using this expression:

$$\frac{C}{L+C} = \frac{\frac{1}{4}}{\frac{2}{4} + \frac{1}{4}} = \frac{\frac{1}{4}}{\frac{3}{4}} = \frac{1}{3} \quad (2)$$

Figure 1: The geometric series for $S(4) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{4^j}$: In this figure we can see that we are setting aside the red square so that we can further split. We can also see that after the red one is set aside that green square becomes $\frac{1}{3}$ of the remaining squares. Then in the next step we then start focusing on just the red square for further subdivisions, and so on. And since this will happen at every step, we can see that for $x=4$ the sum must be $\frac{1}{3}$. Note here that $C = 1$, $S = 1$, and $L = 2$.

2.1.2 The alternating infinite series for $S(4) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{-1}{(-4)^{n+1}}$

Now let's see how this approach works for the alternating infinite series for $x = 4$. In the above example for the geometric infinite series we chose 1 square and set another square aside for further splittings. But now we are trying to take away a *-ve* proportion rather than a *+ve* one and if we return to my idea about holes we can see that since we are removing a hole, which in itself is *-ve*, we must add something back. In fact it leaves us with exactly one square to add rather than remove.

Figure 2: The alternating infinite series for $S(4) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{-1}{(-4)^{n+1}}$: Here since we are taking away a negative we must add a new green square rather than take away from any of the original four squares. Since I have chosen one additional square (green) I must set aside an additional square for the next step (which is the red square). Hence the value of $C = 1$, $S = 1$, and $L = 4$. If we set aside the red square for future splittings this means that our chosen green square now represents $\frac{1}{5}$ of squares under consideration at this step. At the next step focusing on just the red square, we will end up again with just $\frac{1}{5}$ of the squares under consideration. And since this will happen at every step, we can see that for $x=4$ the sum: $\frac{1}{4} - \frac{1}{4^2} + \frac{1}{4^3} - \dots = \frac{1}{5}$.

2.2 An example for $x=2$

2.2.1 The geometric series for $S(2) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^j}$

Here we split a shape into two pieces. One being red to set aside ($S = 1$) and a green one that is chosen ($C = 1$). If we leave the red box this leaves us with only the green box causing it to become $\frac{1}{1}$ of the total pieces under consideration at that stage ($L = 0$). If we do the same thing to the red box at the next step we will again get $\frac{1}{1}$, and so on. Therefore the overall fraction will always be $\frac{1}{1}$ or just simply 1. This can be seen below in **Figure 3**. Again we can see that the fraction represented as an expression is: $\frac{C}{L+C}$. This shows that:

$$\frac{C}{L+C} = \frac{\frac{1}{2}}{0 + \frac{1}{2}} = \frac{\frac{1}{2}}{\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{1}{1} = 1 \quad (3)$$

Figure 3: The geometric series for $S(2) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{2^j}$: In this figure we can see two squares, one being red set aside for future use, and the other green which is chosen, leaving none left out. Therefore at each step we always take a proportion $\frac{1}{1}$ at each step ($C = 1$, $S = 1$, and $L = 0$). And since this will happen at every step, we can see that for $x=2$ the sum must be $\frac{1}{1}$ or 1.

2.2.2 The alternating infinite series for $S(2) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{-1}{(-2)^{n+1}}$

For the alternating infinite series when $x = 2$ we can imagine that we have two boxes, each being a half of a bigger shape. In the example of the positive geometric infinite series we chose one of these boxes and the other was set aside to continue splitting. This meant that we ended up with 1 as our final answer. However, in this paper we are removing a negative. If we once again visit the hole idea we can see that we are removing a negative

hole. This means that we are actually adding an additional square. See **Figure 4**.

Figure 4: The alternating infinite series for $S(2) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{-1}{(-2)^{n+1}}$: We start with 2 blue squares, which will be left out and cannot be used, we add one additional square because we have to take away -1 (green), and create another square for further splitting (red). At the first step the green square is one of 3 squares under consideration and therefore represent a proportion of $\frac{1}{3}$ (because the red box is being set aside for the next stage). And since this will happen at every step, we can see that for $x=2$ the sum must be $\frac{1}{3}$. $C = 1$, $S = 1$, and $L = 2$, which means $\frac{C}{L+C} = \frac{1}{2} - \frac{1}{2^2} + \frac{1}{2^3} - \dots = \frac{1}{3}$.

3 General Result

I consider here the general result.

3.1 The General Result for any number $x > 1$

3.1.1 The geometric series for $S(x) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{x^j}$ for any number $x > 1$

Using the previous examples I will now consider the case for any number $x > 1$. In the positive geometric infinite series we were taking away a positive fraction. This means that if we start $T = 1$ square, with $T = C + S + L$, if we take away a proportion $\frac{1}{x}$ we can determine the values for C , S , and L . As we are choosing a proportion of $\frac{1}{x}$, $C = \frac{1}{x}$. This means we must set $S = \frac{1}{x}$ as well, leaving $L = 1 - \frac{1}{x} - \frac{1}{x}$. The sum, using the expression (See **Figure 5**) is:

$$\frac{C}{L+C} = S(x) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{x^j} = \frac{1}{x-1} \quad (4)$$

Figure 5: The geometric series for $S(x) = \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{x^j}$: Here we start with $T = 1$ square, choosing $\frac{1}{x}$ proportions out of it. Therefore $C = \frac{1}{x}$ and we must set $S = \frac{1}{x}$, leaving $L = 1 - \frac{1}{x} - \frac{1}{x}$. This means that the sum must be $\frac{C}{L+C} = \frac{1}{x-1}$.

3.1.2 The alternating infinite series for $S(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{-1}{(-x)^{n+1}}$ for $x > 1$

For the alternating infinite series for any $x > 1$ we can start with $T = x$ boxes. Here we have to remove -1 box (equal to a proportion of $\frac{-1}{x}$). But we know that removing a negative 1 is the same as adding +1 (green box). This means that $C = 1$ and we must add another box to be set aside, meaning $S = 1$. This means that L must be equal to x . And the sum using the expression (See **Figure 6**) is:

$$\frac{C}{L+C} = S(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{-1}{(-x)^{n+1}} = \frac{1}{x+1} \quad (5)$$

Figure 6: The alternating infinite series for $S(x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{-1}{(-x)^{n+1}}$: Here we start with $T = x$ squares. Here we can see that instead of taking away +1 from x we are taking away -1 which means we have to add an additional square (green), equivalent to taking away a proportion $\frac{-1}{x}$. This means $C = 1$, and we must create another square (red) to be set aside, $S = 1$. Since we created two new boxes and did not take any away, $L = T = x$, and the expression $\frac{C}{L+C} = \frac{1}{x+1}$.

This is the general result.

4 Discussion

If we look at the general results, equations 4 and 5 above, we can see that the same geometric method of choosing a certain number of boxes C and setting aside an equal number of boxes S to leave $L = T - C - S$ from a starting number of T boxes gives us the ability to write the final sum of both the geometric and alternating infinite series as $\frac{C}{L+C}$ for any number $x > 1$.